

PHOTOPOLYMERIZABLE HYBRID COMPOSITIONS BASED ON (THERMO)PHOTOSENSITIVE MONOMER UNITS USED ORGANIC MATRIX FOR SILVER AND ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research was to obtain and characterize hybrid polymer composites incorporating ZnO (prior prepared by using microwave irradiation), Ag nanoparticles or a combination of them into photopolymerizable monomer compositions based on new acrylic urethane monomers/macromers and hybrid monomers with silyl groups in structure. Additionally, the photocatalytic effect of the photopolymerized hybrid films was investigated by testing the decomposition rate of the Nile Red dye under UV irradiation, the obtained results suggesting that such materials could be used as photocatalyst for dyes.

1 INTRODUCTION

There has been considerable interest in recent years on fabricating nanoparticle assemblies because they represent a modern concept in nanoscience/nanotechnology and a popular route toward the preparation of advanced functional materials. Because the polymer-nanoparticle (NP) composites may have novel and improved properties originating from the synergism between organic and inorganic component, they have found a large applicability in many important areas such as coatings, inks, dental materials, optical elements, photoresists, electron devices, and so on. One of common methods used for producing of polymer/NPs composites involves a photochemical approach for the in situ synthesis of metal NPs and particularly, noble metals (silver, gold), created during the photopolymerization of some liquid monomers incorporating metal salts as nanoparticles precursors [1]. In order to exploit the unique properties of such materials it is needed that the stabilized nanostructures through host-guest interactions be uniformly distributed in the organic matrix, where the aggregation phenomenon has to be avoided. In fact, the choice of the polymer is a key factor that affects the particles properties with a narrow size distribution and the final properties of nanohybrids intended for a specific application.

Among these hybrid materials, a special attention was also given to the composites with ZnO, known for the luminescent properties, high and optical transparency in the near UV/ visible regions, and electric conductivity [2-4], useful in the development of optical and optoelectronic devices, photocatalysis, gas sensors, fibers, coatings, and the others [5-7]. In general, the obtaining of such hybrids and especially, the homogeneity of dispersion of the inorganic component into the organic phase, as well as the stabilization of particles size without aggregation of the ZnO structures [8] continue to raise often problems. However, the exploration of ZnO/polymer nanocomposites is a subject of great importance in both fundamental and applied research.

In connection, our present study presents the synthesis and characterization of novel urethane monomers to be used in the obtaining of photopolymerized composites with ZnO particles, Ag nanoparticles and their mixture aiming improvement of some properties of the final materials. Besides, spectral measurements of the composite films in presence of Nile Red dye were performed in order to evaluate their potential use in the photocatalytic degradation of dye through simultaneous acquisition of the UV/vis spectra and fluorescence spectra.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

(-)-Borneol, 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate, dibutyltin dilaurat, phenyl-bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (Irgacure 819), silver nitrate (AgNO_3), zinc acetate dihydrate, hexamethylenetetramine (HMT), trisodium citrate, 1,4-dioxan, N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPA), Nile Red were used as received (Aldrich).

2.2 Synthesis of ZnO

The ZnO nanoparticles were produced using zinc acetate dihydrate and hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) as the zinc cation and hydroxide anion precursors, respectively. The precursor solution was prepared by dissolving 2 g of zinc acetate and 7 g of HMT in deionized water under vigorous stirring at room temperature. Then 1.2 g of trisodium citrate was added to the aqueous solution. The resulting solution was irradiated by a temperature controlled microwave system at 90 °C for 15 min. The white precipitate obtained upon irradiation was alternatively washed several times with deionized water and ethanol after filtration, and dried in an oven.

2.3 Synthesis of bornyl methacrylate (BM)

For the synthesis of bornyl methacrylate (BM), 5 g (33.4 mmol) of (-)-borneol, and 4.81 ml (33.4 mmol) of 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate dissolved in 20 ml dioxane were reacted using dibutyltin dilaurat as catalyst. The course of the reaction was monitored through the infrared spectroscopy following the isocyanate stretching band ($\sim 2260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) up to its disappearance. The reaction mixture was stirred at 38 °C for 24 hours and then the resulting viscous monomer was collected after removing the solvent using a rotary vacuum evaporator.

FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3361 (HN-COO); 2955 and 2879 (C-H stretching); 1722 (C=O), 1638 and 814 (C=C); 1298 (C-O-C). ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 (δ , ppm): 6.13 and 5.59 (H from $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}$), 5.02 (NH), 4.82 (CHOCO), 4.23 (CH_2OCO), 3.50 (CH_2), 1.95 ($\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1.87-1.01 (H from bornyl) and 0.90 (H_3C).

^{13}C NMR in CDCl_3 (δ , ppm): 167.09 and 157.91 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 135.80 and 125.67 ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 80.04 and 44.45 (CH from bornyl), 27.82, 27.03 and 20.25 (CH_2 from bornyl), 49.23 and 48.51 (quaternary C from bornyl), 63.49 and 39.83 (CH_2), 19.49, 18.03 and 13.26 (CH_3).

2.4 Film preparation

The polymer films based on bornyl methacrylate (BM), triethoxysilylpropyl carbamoyloxyethyl methacrylate (TCM), poly(propylene glycol) dimethacrylate (PO-UDMA) and N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPA) were obtained directly via photopolymerization using phenyl-bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (Irgacure 819) as photoinitiator. The photopolymerization process was carried out using a Hg-Xe lamp with a light intensity of 40 mW/cm^2 , in air atmosphere.

2.5 Measurements

The structure of derivatives was verified by FTIR, ^1H (^{13}C) NMR, UV/visible and fluorescence spectroscopies. ^1H (^{13}C) NMR and FTIR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400MHz spectrometer in CDCl_3 at room temperature, and on Bruker Vertex 70 instrument, respectively. Irradiation of the

polymer solutions containing the silver salt were carried out using UV light with intensity of 40 mW/cm² generated by an Hg-Xe lamp (Hamamatsu Lightningcure Type LC58, Model L9588). The UV/vis absorption spectra were measured with a Specord 200 spectrophotometer in film state, in the spectral range 300–800 nm. The formulations were coated onto glass slides by using a wire-wound applicator to yield polymer films with thickness of about 100 μm. The photodegradation experiments were carried out in quartz spectrophotometric cells using for irradiation the same Hg-Xe lamp at room temperature, the samples being placed at 5 cm distance. TEM measurements and microscopic investigations were achieved at 100 kV using a Hitachi High-Tech HT7700 instrument and an environmental scanning electron microscope QUANTA200 coupled with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscope (ESEM/EDX), respectively. For microwave irradiation it was used a CEM Discover apparatus at temperature of 90 °C, a power of 250 W and a pressure of 5 psi. The surface morphology was investigated with a SOLVER PRO-M atomic force microscope (AFM). For this experiment, the formulations were photopolymerized on silica wafers. The fluorescence intensity measurements were performed with a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 spectrophotometer at room temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis and characterization

Bornyl methacrylate (BM) was prepared by a classical two-step addition reaction of borneol to 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate in the presence of dibutyltin dilaurat as catalyst, whereas triethoxysilylpropyl carbamoyloxyethyl methacrylate (TCM) and poly(propylene glycol) dimethacrylate (PO-UDMA) were synthesized according to the reported data [9]. All these monomers (Scheme 1) were used in the preparation of polymeric composites with 1 wt.% AgNO₃ and/or ZnO incorporated before photopolymerization.

Scheme 1: Structures of TCM, BM, PO-UDMA and NIPA monomers used in photopolymerization reactions.

The molecular structure of bornyl methacrylate was confirmed through ¹H NMR analysis. The ¹H NMR spectrum of BM showed in Figure 1 reveals the signals characteristic to the olefinic protons (6.13 and 5.59 ppm) in trans/cis configuration, methyne protons from ester urethane (4.82 ppm) and methylene protons (3.50 ppm) linked to the urethane group, together with the methylene from ester (4.23 ppm) and methyl protons (1.95 ppm) from the methacrylate. Other characteristic signals are given by the methyne, methylene and methyl protons from bornyl positioned in the region 1.87-1.01 ppm and at 0.90 ppm, respectively.

Figure 1: ^1H NMR spectra of bornyl methacrylate (BM) in CDCl_3 .

The quantity and types of materials used to prepare such composites are given in Table 1.

Sample	PO-UDMA (wt.%)	BM (wt.%)	TCM (wt.%)	NIPA (wt.%)	AgNO_3 (wt.%)	ZnO (wt.%)
A2	70	30	-	-	1	-
A3	70	30	-	-	-	1
A4	70	30	-	-	1	1
B2	70	20	10	-	1	-
B3	70	20	10	-	-	1
B4	70	20	10	-	1	1
N2	70	20	-	10	1	-
N3	70	20	-	10	-	1
N4	70	20	-	10	1	1

Table 1: Composition of the formulations used in our study

The composite materials were synthesized by photopolymerization of the monomer mixture based on urethane dimethacrylate of oligomer type (PO-UDMA) and bornyl methacrylate (70:30 wt/wt) with 1 wt.% AgNO_3 , ZnO or AgNO_3 -ZnO for a period of 5 min, in the presence of 1.5 wt.% Irgacure 819 used as photoinitiator, until thin films were produced (A2-A4). In the case of B2-B4 formulations, triethoxysilylpropyl carbamoyloxyethyl methacrylate (TCM, 10 wt.%) was taken as co-monomer besides PO-UDMA and BM, AgNO_3 , ZnO or AgNO_3 -ZnO. Given the presence of triethoxysilylpropyl moieties in the polymer matrix, the photopolymerized films were further kept at room temperature for about 7 days to advance the hydrolysis and condensation reactions with the formation of siloxane linkages. By replacement of TCM from each formulation with N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPA, 10 wt.%) other polymer films (N2-N4) were also obtained under the adopted experimental conditions. Figure 2

presents the spectral changes that occur in the infrared spectra of the formulations containing 1 wt.% ZnO after UV irradiation.

Figure 2: FTIR-ATR spectra of the formulations A3, B3 and N3 containing 1 wt.% ZnO and the spectrum of ZnO (inset).

The first spectra displays the characteristic absorption bands at 3343 cm^{-1} (urethane NH), 2970 cm^{-1} (C-H), 1719 cm^{-1} (CO), 1257 cm^{-1} and at 1097 cm^{-1} (C-O-C), while for the N3 film the absorption bands for amide I (1651 cm^{-1}) and amide II (1534 cm^{-1}) become visible. In Figure 2 (inset) the FTIR spectra of ZnO contains an absorption band at 3434 cm^{-1} attributed to the hydroxyl groups, together with Zn-O bands located at 1569 cm^{-1} and 653-694 cm^{-1} .

Additionally, the surface profile of the films was examined by AFM technique, which shows a 3D topographical visualization of the B3/ZnO hybrid composite and the B3 pure film. As shown in Figure 3, the presence of ZnO nanoparticles in the polymer matrix determined a significantly decrease of the average roughness value from 0.86 nm to 0.31 nm.

Figure 3: AFM images for B3 film (left) and its corresponding hybrid with 1 wt.% ZnO (right).

The particles obtained in this manner were characterized by UV/vis spectroscopy, where it is possible to identify specific features of the particles incorporated in the formulations B3 and B4 or photogenerated during the UV irradiation process (B2, B4). In Figure 4 the appearance of a small absorption maximum at 380 nm is attributed to the ZnO nanoparticles (B3), while the absorption maxima at 441 nm (B2) and 435 nm (B4) belong to the surface plasmon resonance of the Ag nanoparticles.

Figure 4: UV/vis characteristics of the ZnO, Ag and Ag-ZnO nanoparticles from the B2-B4 composite films.

The morphology, elemental and spatial distribution of the zinc, silver and silicon atoms formed within the polymer matrix was investigated by ESEM/EDX (Fig. 5 and Table 2). In the resulting EDX pattern (Fig. 5b, d, f) derived from the SEM images (Fig. 5a, c, e) of the films taken in fracture, we can notice the appearance of characteristic peaks for C, O, N, Zn, Ag and Si, proving that the composites with zinc and silver nanoparticles were successfully prepared. Furthermore, mapping images of zinc, silver and silicon atoms (Fig. 5b, d and f inset), show through the presence of bright spots a uniform distribution of the atoms inside the matrix. The EDX analysis provided a quantitative estimation of the inorganic phase into the polymer matrix, in which the content of ZnO was found to be between 0.57 and 0.89 wt.%. It can appreciate that the content of the Ag atoms in the investigate films varied between 0.62 and 0.97 wt.%, and the Si atoms were around 0.74 and 1.37.

Sample	C (%)	O (%)	N (%)	Zn (%)	Ag (%)	Si (%)
A2	76.38	19.83	3.01	-	0.78	-
A3	76.59	19.68	3.09	0.64	-	-
A4	76.48	20.46	1.87	0.57	0.62	-
B2	75.21	21.31	1.99	-	0.75	0.74
B3	73.65	21.14	3.44	0.76	-	1.01
B4	72.59	21.78	2.50	0.89	0.87	1.37
N2	77.29	18.47	3.27	-	0.97	-
N3	77.42	19.09	2.78	0.71	-	-
N4	77.35	18.14	2.94	0.74	0.83	-

Table 2: EDX elemental microanalysis.

Figure 5: SEM image of A4 (a), B4 (c) and N4 (e) in fracture, the EDX analysis results for A4 (b), B4 (d) and N4 (f) and mapping images for silver, zinc and silicon elements (inset).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was also performed to establish the size and morphology of the silver and zinc particles from the above synthesized nanocomposites. TEM images (Fig. 6) collected on the hybrid films A4 and B4 suggested the existence of particles with spherical shape and sizes between 5 and 20 nm (ZnO), and around 5 nm for in situ photogenerated silver nanoparticles. It can be seen that the both types of nanoparticles are more agglomerated in the film A4 compared to B4, where there is a more uniform distribution of them, most probable caused by composition of the formulation.

Figure 6: TEM images and statistical size distribution of the ZnO nanoparticles (a) and of silver and zinc nanoparticles dispersed into A4 (b) and B4 (c).

3.2 Photodegradation experiments of Nile Red

We began by examining the photocatalytic degradation of Nile Red (NR) dye upon UV irradiation in the presence of B4 composite film, used as catalyst. Hence, the changes in fluorescence and UV/vis spectra of NR dye by B4 film containing ZnO and Ag nanoparticles under UV exposure for different times are plotted in Fig. 7a,b. The decrease of the emission and absorption band intensities of the dye in ethanol solution sustains a fast degradation in presence of hybrid composite tested as photocatalyst. As it can be observed from this figure, the disappearance of the characteristic band of NR dye (558 nm) after 15 min of UV irradiation indicates that NR was degraded around 93.6% by the polymer/ZnO-Ag film.

Figure 7: Modifications in fluorescence (a) and UV/vis absorption (b) spectra of NR dye for different irradiation time in presence of B4 hybrid film. Spectral changes of the NR in absence/presence of the composites films with respect to time intervals (c); kinetic evaluation of the decomposition process of Nile Red(d).

In the same time, the fluorescence measurements showed that the fluorescence intensity of NR located at 632 nm decreased at 99 %, confirming again that the degradation of the NR dye occurred. Under these experimental conditions, the degradation percentage of NR induced after 10 min of UV irradiation by our hybrid composite films is around 66 % in the presence of A3 film (with ZnO), 91.7% for A4 (ZnO-Ag), 52% for B3 (ZnO), 83.8% for B4 (ZnO-Ag) and for N3 (ZnO) and N4 (ZnO-Ag) at 65.9% and 97.5%, respectively. The percentage of degradation measured at different times of irradiation was calculated by normalizing the peak intensity in term of the starting ($t = 0$) band intensity of NR in the presence of catalyst (Fig. 7c).

On the other hand, the degradation rate constant was determined from the slope obtained by linear regression from a plot of the natural logarithm of the normalized absorbance as a function of irradiation time (Fig. 7d). Consequently, the UV photolysis of NR occurred with rate constants varying between $2.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (in the presence of B3 with ZnO) and of $1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (in the presence of N4 with ZnO-Ag). Therefore, the photodegradation of NR depend not only on the structural factors, but also on the compositional parameters of the polymer films with ZnO alone or ZnO-Ag nanoparticles, for which reason other studies will be taken in consideration in our group.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A series of hybrid nanocomposites based on different photopolymerizable monomers and ZnO, Ag or ZnO-Ag nanoparticles introduced before photopolymerization in the monomer mixture or in situ photogenerated were obtained and characterized by spectral and microscopic methods. The composites containing ZnO and ZnO-Ag nanoparticles uniformly dispersed in the polymer matrix can be used as catalyst in the photocatalytic degradation of NR dye upon UV irradiation, as demonstrated by UV/vis and fluorescence measurements.

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